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Research Article

**PREFERENCE FOR MALE AND FEMALE MENTORS AMONG
THE MEDICAL STUDENTS OF ALLAMA IQBAL MEDICAL
COLLEGE, LAHORE**¹Dr. Aiesha Qadeer, ²Dr. Arslan Ali, ³Dr Azka Awan¹House Officer D.G Khan Medical College D.G Khan²Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur³Allied Hospital Fiasalabad**Abstract:**

Background: This research is based on evaluating the relative preferences of mentors based on gender by the students of Allama Iqbal Medical College. A mentor is someone who is tasked with imparting knowledge to students. To determine the effect of the mentors' gender on teaching effectiveness we distributed questionnaires to the students from 1st to 5th year M.B.B.S.

Objective: To determine the relative preferences of either male or female mentors by the medical students.

Method: It was a cross sectional study on the students of Allama Iqbal Medical College (1st to final year), public sector college affiliated with Jinnah Hospital from April 2016 to June 2016. A sample of 300 students was selected. Sampling technique was convenient sampling.

Data collection and Analysis: 60 students per class were given a questionnaire on basis of convenient sampling, containing 20 questions each. The data was analyzed using SPSS-21.0.

Results: In a sample size of 300, 44% preferred male mentors and 18.3% preferred female mentors while the rest had no preference based on gender.

Conclusion: Most of the students had preferred male mentors to females, based on certain attitudes that they believe the male teachers had. However, these people comprise less than half of the sample size, with a major portion not having any preference and a small portion favoring female teachers.

Keywords: Mentor, Student, Gender.

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INTRODUCTION:

Mentor is someone who is considered a wise and trusted guide as well as an advisor (i). Teacher is also another term used alternatively for a mentor. There are many causes as to why students are more satisfied by one gender over the other when considering a mentor. Some students may find it easier to communicate with a teacher and relate to them if they are of the same gender as themselves. In an American study conducted in 2010, 'the role model effect' of teachers' gender on students' achievement stated that students would be more satisfied, both academically and intellectually when taught by the teacher of the same gender (ii). Similarly, the 'gender stereotypical model' stated that boys do better when taught by male teachers and vice versa, as the male teachers could handle them and inspire them better (iii). Another study conducted in South Korea, revealed that girls are more satisfied by female mentors as they are looking for a more nurturing relationship with teachers, which is best provided by female teachers (iv). An article published in Netherlands, illustrated that female teachers are better for both male and female students, as they are usually more tolerant and have lesser conflicts with boys (v). The 'superiority' of the female teachers over their male counterparts is of small magnitude (vi). North Carolina State University's study claimed that students tend to give lower ratings to teachers if they are females (vii). Online students' ratings of teachers described male teachers as "brilliant, intelligent and smart" while females were described as "mean or unfair" (viii-ix). These ratings are consistent with stereotypically gendered expectations. Biasing may be based on the fact that female teachers are perceived harsher than males (x). During students' reviews of teachers in 2015, 70 out of 1 million female teachers were described as "incompetent" (xi).

According to a study by Taylor J., opposite teacher-student gender has an adverse effect on students' academic score but it varies subject to subject (xii). A study in, depicted that it is the teachers' knowledge, nature and background but not gender that reflects the teaching effectiveness and student's satisfaction. (xiii).

An Asian study in 2010 concluded that the students' satisfaction is determined by the factors like, subject interest, emotional intelligence and students' ability rather than the gender of the teacher (xiv). Choosing right kind of candidate is more logical (xv). Above all, it is the competence of the teacher that matters and not the gender (xvi). A Pakistani article published in 2013, suggested that females, due to their better emotional intelligence, make better

teachers as students are more content with them (xvii). Males tend to perform better in masculine role (xviii). A survey in Pakistan demonstrated that 76% and 63% of male and female students, respectively, favor the teachers of same gender as themselves (xix).

To conclude, gender has a major role to play in the way teachers are viewed, even in this modern era. However, the degree to which gender impacts on students' satisfaction and the overall teaching acumen of teachers is debatable.

Medicine is ceasing to be a male dominated field with not only greater female doctors but also more female professors. The main reason for conducting our study is to access the preference for the teacher's gender, especially now that there is greater number of female medical students than males.

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

Study Design: It is a cross sectional study.

Study setting: Allama Iqbal Medical College established in 1975, is a co-educational college of medicine, nursing and allied health sciences located at Allama Shabbir Ahmed Usmani Road, Lahore Pakistan. Total strength of college is about 1700 students. College is affiliated with Jinnah hospital which is a tertiary care Govt. hospital in Lahore Punjab.

Duration of Study: April 2016-june 2016.

Sample Size: 300 medical students.

Sampling Technique: Convenient Sampling.

Operational Definition: A **mentor** facilitates personal and professional growth in an individual by sharing the knowledge and insights that have been learned through years of experience. Student is a person enrolled at an institution who studies a particular academic subject. Gender is one having identity with regard to individuality as male and female.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Both male and female students of 1st to final year M.B.B.S.
2. Boarders and Day Scholars.
3. Who will give consent and fill the questionnaire.

Exclusion Criteria:

All those medical students who are eligible to fill questionnaire but are not giving consent.

Variables:

Independent: Age, sex and academic year.

Dependent: Preference for male and female mentor among students.

Qualitative: Sex

Quantitative: Age and number of students from each class.

Data collection:

A questionnaire was developed and distributed among the male and female medical students of Allama Iqbal Medical College. Participation was voluntarily and confidentiality of the students was assured.

Data analysis:

Data analysis was done by SPSS-21 version. Frequency and percentage were determined for all the qualitative variables. Mean and standard deviations was found for all the quantitative variables.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Age of students - Frequency table:

Age of students	Frequency	Percentage
17-19	75	25.0
20-22	172	57.3
23-25	53	17.7
Total	300	100.0

Table 2: Gender of students – Frequency table:

Gender of students	Frequency	Percentage
Male	148	49.3
Female	152	50.7
Total	300	100.0

Table 3: Better mentor- Gender Cross tabulation

	Gender of the teacher	Gender of the students		Total
		Male	Female	
Who do you think is a better mentor?	Male	62	70	132
	Female	37	18	55
	Both	49	64	113
Total		148	152	300

Table 4: Better mentor –Gender Chi square test

	Value (x2)	df	p value
Person chi square	8.988	2	0.011

Table 5: Better role model - Gender Cross tabulation

Gender of the students.	Who proves to be a better role model for the students?			Total
	Male	Female	Both	
Male	76	26	46	148
Female	46	24	82	152
Total	122	50	128	300

GRAPH 1:

Pie chart 1.1: Showing 34% (102) students agree that it is easier to approach teacher of same gender.
GRAPH 2:

Pie chart 1.2: Showing that 37.46% (112) students agree that male teachers are more brilliant.

GRAPH 3:

Pie chart 1.3: Showing that 37.33% (112) students think that male teachers are more dedicated towards their profession.

GRAPH 4:

Bar chart 1.1: Showing that 37.67% (113) agree that female teachers are politer and nurturing.

GRAPH 5:

Bar chart 1.2: Showing that 20.62% (62) students agree that male teachers have more conflicts with their students.

RESULTS:

The study was conducted on M.B.B.S. students from 1st year to final year of Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore. The sample size was 300 students consisting of 50.66% females (152) and 49.33% males (148). Out of 300, 44% (132 students) preferred male mentors out of which 46.9% (62) were males and 53.03% (70) were females. Those who preferred female mentors were 18.3% (55) students consisting of 37 males and 18 females). Chi square test was applied and the results were found to be significant ($\chi^2 = 8.988$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.01$).

About 43% (129 students) agreed that both male and female teachers are equally good role models. Those who chose male mentors were 40.66% (122 students with 76 males and 26 females) while 16% (50 students, 26 males and 24 females) chose female mentors as better role models. The Chi-Square test results were insignificant ($\chi^2 = 17.532$, $df = 2$). A majority of the answers, 37.3% (112) thought that both male and female teachers are equally dedicated towards their profession while 35.3% (106) students thought that males are more dedicated while 27.3% (82) students thought that female teachers are more dedicated. In our research, when students were asked if male teachers were more brilliant and intelligent than their female counterparts, 37.46% (112) students agreed, 25.42% (76) students were neutral, 23.08% (69) strongly agreed, 10.70% (32) disagreed and 3.34% (10) strongly disagreed. Regarding the question of who is politer and has a nurturing attitude, 37.67% (113) agreed that female teachers

are politer and have a more nurturing attitude as compared to their male colleagues, 25% (75) students were neutral, 18.33% (55) strongly agreed, 14.33% (43) disagreed, while 4.67% (14) students strongly disagreed. When asked if male teachers have more conflicts with their students, 30.33% of the respondents (91) were neutral, 29.33% (88 students) disagreed, 20.67% (62 students) agreed, 12% (36) strongly agreed and 7.67% (23) strongly disagreed.

A vast majority of the students found it easier to approach the teacher of the same gender with 34% (102) students agreeing that they feel more comfortable with the teacher with the same gender as themselves, 32.63% (98) strongly agreeing, 16.67% (50) being neutral, 11.67% (35) disagreeing while 5% (15) strongly disagreeing.

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of this research was to determine the preferences of male or female mentors by the student of medical college. We predicted that the students would prefer male mentors over female mentors. Although most of the students claimed to prefer male mentors to female mentors, they graded some attributes higher in the female mentors than in the male mentors.

While the male teachers were described as better role models and more 'dedicated', 'brilliant' or 'intelligent' they also gave overwhelming support to the idea that the male teachers are ones who have more conflicts with their students (8). The female teachers were, all in all, considered by most as being

politer and nurturing than their male colleagues. This is consistent with previous research on the subject, one conducted in South Korea (4) and the other in Netherlands (5). Our study also reveals that, generally, students find it easier to approach a teacher of the same gender. The 'Gender Stereotypical Model' also supports this, with previous research confirming that students tend to perform better when taught by teacher with the same gender (3). This model, however, does not work for all students as a study found that this 'gender match' may be more beneficial for female students than for males (5) which is in contrast with our study in which most of the students have preferred male teachers over female teachers.

Our study differed slightly from previous research in Pakistan as only 41% of males and 11% of females prefer a teacher with the same gender compared to 76% and 63% of male and female students, respectively, from the previous study (19). Our study also found that female teachers are regarded as having a higher emotional intelligence than the males with more students feeling that they are more 'kind' and 'caring'. Indeed, research states that emotional intelligence is needed to be successful in the world of academia (17).

Overall, the teaching abilities of a teacher are dependent on the teachers' competence and not on gender, it is stated that the way to improve the educational system is to improve the quality of quality of teaching and learning, and not on selecting teachers based on gender.

CONCLUSION:

To sum up the findings, gender has no absolute role when it comes to the teaching quality or effectiveness of a mentor. Both male and female mentors are graded separately on their knowledge and skills of their subjects. The students have no specific preference for male mentors as we originally thought, although they may state that males are better in some areas of teaching, female teachers are also considered fairly competent in their role as educators.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

PREFERENCE FOR MALE AND FEMALE MENTORS AMONG THE MEDICAL STUDENTS OF ALLAMA IQBAL MEDICAL COLLEGE, LAHORE

Serial No: _____ Name: _____
 Age: _____ Gender _____ Class: _____

Tick the appropriate option. Multiple options will not be entertained.

1. Who do you think is a better mentor?
 (a) Male (b) Females (c) Both
2. Who do you think is more dedicated towards his/her profession?
 (a) Male Teachers (b) Female Teachers (c) Both
3. Who do you think better engages and holds attention of the students in all the discussions?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
4. Who ensures better availability and easier approach for the students?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
5. Who can better maintain the decorum of the class?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
6. Who delivers better, precise, conceptual and student-centered lessons?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
7. Who is more punctual?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
8. Who is more compassionate (takes personal problems into consideration) and empathetic towards the students?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
9. Who is more inspirational?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
10. Who proves to be a better role model for the students?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
11. Who welcomes the quires of the students and gives them a satisfactory response?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
12. Who do you prefer for career guidance?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
13. Who do you think is more trustworthy?
 (a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher (c) Both
14. Did you ever feel that changing the gender of your teacher had any impact on your academic results?
 (a) Yes (b) No
15. If yes, which gender has more positive impact on your academics?

(a) Male Teacher (b) Female Teacher

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
16. Male teachers are more brilliant and intelligent.					
17. Female teachers are politer and have a more nurturing attitude.					
18. Male teachers have more conflicts with their students.					
19. Attendance is generally lower in classes held by the female teachers.					
20. Students find it easier to approach the teacher of their own gender					